

Debates on Same-Sex Marriage in India: Interplay between Legislative Enactments and Social Exclusion

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Abstract

The idea of same sex union is not a modern concept having roots in classical Indian traditions. Modernity comes along with it the concept of certainty and clarity. Therefore it tends to legalize or ban unfamiliar relations. Legally, the history of Same Sex Marriage is not that old with Taiwan and Nepal being the two Asian countries to recognize it. In India, a section of the queer community are raising pleas to legalize such marriages because such recognition can benefit them in terms of property rights, adoption, and significant decisions to partner's life. However, the five benches Supreme Court decision with legal lens again failed to recognize such union. In a multi-cultural country like India, why acts like Special Marriage Act is still limited to religious and community based rigidities? The following paper tries to look concepts like Same-Sex Marriage and relations not only from legal angle but from the realities of the society. Social exclusion nonetheless is a deep-rooted cultural reality.

Keywords: Personal Laws, Same Sex Marriage, Social Recognition, Substantial Question of Law

Introduction

The Same Sex Marriage agenda raised within the goals of common LGBTQ+ movements is only over two decades old. The current millennium has already witnessed several countries enacting special enactments for homosexual unions using expressions like civil partnership, civil union or domestic partnership. Back in 2000, Netherland was the first country to legalise same sex union. Following the trend, several North American, South American, European, and the government of South Africa recognized homosexual matrimonial alliances. But in the case of Asia, the history of same sex marriage is not that old. Till date, only Taiwan has legalized same sex marriage.

The debates of same sex marriage in India have led to some interesting turn on events. Following the recent trend of the Indian Politics, it started to look back to the basic structure and philosophy of the Constitution. The debate that was going regarded it as the "substantial question of law as to the interpretation" of the constitution. However, the Supreme court five constitutional bench did not legalized Same Sex Marriage under Special Marriage Act even though it acknowledged the right to self determination.

History of the Legal Battle

Certain notable Supreme Court verdicts can be seen as the predecessors to the recent same sex marriage pleas. In the Naaz Foundation case in 2009, Justice AP Shah of Delhi high court upheld that the outdated colonial IPC provision ultra vires the Constitution of India. A number of petitions since then has been filed seeking their recognition. The Puttuswamy Judgment, 2017 affirms the right to privacy as a fundamental right. Following that the Navtej Johar Judgment in 2018 finally decriminalized same sex relationships. The historic abrogation of section 377 of the IPC in 2019 can be seen as the landmark situation deviating from the colonial legal provisions.

The Dual Sides of the Debate

Emphasizing on both sides of the debate, according to petitions submitted, "... The State does not recognise these other forms of marriages or unions or personal understandings of relationships between individuals in a society but at the same time is not considering it unlawful".

But only decriminalising homosexuality won't solve the primordial issues associated with social recognition like matrimonial alliances. The battle which the petitioners are fighting are about demanding equal recognition from the State and the liberty to take major decisions with their partners on several aspects similar to any heterosexual couple. A queer couple till the present date, can't take major medical decisions of their partners. Even in matters like law of inheritance, or when the question of adoption arrives, the State does not acknowledge them legally. For example, following the CARA (Central Adoption Resource Authority) regulations, a homosexual couple can adopt a child individually not as a couple.

Such kind of State practices is interpreted as the violation of the fundamental rights of the Constitution including Right to Equality, Right to Life, Privacy and Dignity.

On the other hand, Centre has claimed that approval to same sex marriage would overturn existing legislative enactments. Particularly, legislative laws like Hindu Marriage Act 1955, Parsi Marriage and Divorce Act 1936, Christian Marriage Act 1872, or Foreign Marriage or Divorce Act 1969, which only acknowledge marriages that are heterosexual in nature.

Amending the Special Marriage Act: An Alternative

The Supreme Court has received calls from the LGBTQ+ community in amending the existing Special Marriage Act (1954). As per the received pleas, the Special Marriage Act which was originally enacted to legitimize inter faith marriage is believed to be secular in nature. Therefore, without overturning the existing personal laws, the same sex union can grant recognition through the act. Also, the way Special Marriage Act is written predominantly assumes the parties engaged in a marriage are husband and wife. So they demanded that it should read Spouses replacing any such indications of legally solemnising opposite sex marriage.

Also, a greater demand of amending the heterosexual nature of the Foreign Marriage Act has been articulated through the petitions.

Interestingly in 2014, the World Bank case study titled “The Economic Cost of Homophobia” , estimates that about 1.7% of Indian GDP are sacrificed due to factors related to discrimination of the LGBTQ community. So, the phenomena of Brain Drain are deeply linked with State not legalizing same sex relationships.

From Legal Enactments to Social Prejudices

The problem of such pleas from the LGBTQ+ community does not stop with legal recognition but beyond. However, that does not solve the problem in itself. Issues related to marriage are still subjected to social taboos. The problem is much deeper than expected. It won't be a surprise to witness systematic discrimination even after passage of such social issues on legal grounds, as experienced in Taiwan. While Taiwan has passed the law on pen and paper, but in reality, the same sex couples have to undergo difficult procedures for adoption and surrogacy than any heterosexual couple. Also, the gay and lesbian couples with certain nationalities are still unable to marry their Taiwanese partners.

India can take lessons from the failure of Taiwan in these following areas. However, it seems likely that the social prejudice will persist. Certain open statements passed by the present central government can be seen as an attempt to mainstreamisation of the social institutions like Marriage.

A senior member of the Rajya Sabha has commented undeniably that "same-sex marriage would cause complete havoc with the delicate balance of personal laws in the country” . The RSS General secretary further backs the Centre's stand by claiming marriage in Hinduism is ‘sanskar’, not contract or enjoyment.

Even the Ministry of Law have argued that “Living together as partners and having sexual relationship by same sex individuals ... is not comparable with the Indian family unit concept of a husband, a wife and children,”

These kinds of statements without any hesitation try to reserve the legal recognition of marriage only for the heterosexual couples. So, in that case, all earlier attempts of decriminalizing homosexuality can be seen as act of “sympathetic acceptance rather than inclusion” in the society.

The Alternative Path

So as a way out, many queer activists have called for a complete shift from the existing paradigm of marriage as the only dominant social institution for recognition of any relationship. As Gay activist like Aditiya Tiwari have remarked: queer people should have the freedom to design their relationships. They simply want validation beyond the established common traditional marriage discourse. Accordingly, marriage should not be seen as the only way forward to be part of taking relevant legal decisions in their partner's life.

There has been a common fear among the larger section of the queer community. For them, ever since the decriminalization of section 377, the upper caste, upper class or privileged individuals from the community has been benefited. Such earlier initiatives have left limited impact on the larger population of the LGBTQ+ community who continued to remain ignorant and disadvantaged. There has been similar apprehension among these activists who finds that certain broader problems will remain untouched even if the Supreme Court passes the Same Sex Marriage enactments. So, instead seeking legal recognition for any kind of social relationship (including marriage) would address such broader concerns.

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